

SCALA LECTURE

Composites in Japan

Tsuyoshi Hayashi

Dr., Professor Emeritus, University of Tokyo/President, Japan Plastics Inspection Association, 2-22-13 Yanagibashi, Taito-ku, Tokyo 111, Japan

ABSTRACT

The special needs for composite materials in Japan are firstly considered. Then the status of composites production and applications, a promising area of application, the national R & D project for advanced composites and the source on composites informations in our country are stated.

NEEDS FOR COMPOSITES IN JAPAN

Our country is not only unblest with natural resources, but also small in area, ca $3.77 \times 10^5 \text{km}^2$, to accept a population, ca 120 millions, surrounded by sea and geographically located over the wide range of 3000 km distance from 24° to 46° latitude. The flat ground is only 18% of gross area, hence ca 570m^2 per head.

It is blessed with several volcanic mountain belts, severe typhoons and earthquakes and much rain. The temperature and humidity are high in summer and low in winter. So the structural materials have to bear against severe environmental conditions.

For the above severe conditions, R & D of materials, the saving of materials and energy and those rational utilization have been demanded since long ago in Japan.

The philosophy and basic idea of "Composition" just conform to those needs. Composites will bring us various possibilities for overcoming such severe conditions.

For instance, under corrosive environment, Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP) will provide longer life than conventional materials. Tall building will require stiffer and lighter materials for light-weight structural design. Fiber reinforced Concrete slabs, for example, may have preference for such purpose.

As for a machine or structural design, we can say a lighter one will be stiffer and stronger than a heavier one for the same design load. Composite Materials (CM) will mostly better respond than conventional ones.

The use of a monolithic material for some structural member might be economical in cases. But CM have more design variables (tailor-made properties) and hence greater design flexibilities than monolithic materials. Thus, for demands of diversity with small amount of products in future fashion, CM will be much better adapted than monolithic ones.

In Japan, the living space is very limited and expensive. We have been

heritably forced to make use of it effectively as far as possible. In view of this, the smaller and lighter the better for appliances of daily use. It could be said this will lead to miniaturization of goods. In a transport aircraft, the larger capacity of passenger and luggage room will be preferable. For a limited overall dimensions of an aircraft, CM could make more larger space than aluminum alloy.

As to robotics, it is said it will increase unemployment. In our country, however, the age advancement rate for the last decade is more higher than the other countries and it is now anxious for the shortage of manpower of younger generations. So it is wanted in Japan to develop CM-processing robots which could respond the diversity of needs.

From views mentioned above, it will be understood that CM is a key with high potential for solving various problems in our country.

STATUS OF COMPOSITES PRODUCTION IN JAPAN

Introduction

Composite Materials (CM), showing many varieties in the R & D at present, may be roughly classified into three areas - Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP), Advanced composites (ACM) and diversified functional composites (DCM).

As for the production scale in Japan, GFRP holds the largest share, followed by Carbon Fiber RP (CFRP), Aramid Fiber RP (Kevlar FRP), other CM and those hybrids.

Data of GFRP production is presented here and some recent large and typical GFRP structures and new buds of CM are also introduced.

Data of Recent Production of Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyester

Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyester (GF/UP) is being applied in wide area of industry and has more than 90% share in the production of all GFRP in Japan.

If the application fields are classified as shown in Table 1, we have Table 2 giving those share statistics from 1973 through 1980 for GF/UP (1). As can be seen, there are no remarkable changes of share in each field for recent 8 years.

However, the share for processing methods of GF/UP in Table 3 shows a remarkable increase of moulding compound method in recent years. The SMC and BMC give high reliability and productivity.

Recent Typical FRP Structures

Firstly typical large FRP structures and then the other ones are introduced (2) (3).

(1) Chimneys. In conventional metal - concrete chimneys which are used for exhausting of heavy oil, coal burning and mixed burning boiler gases, the corrosion due to SO_x gases has been a serious problem (2).

For a temperature of 60~70°C of exhaust gas, heat-resistant vinyl-ester and bisphenolic polyester are promising as matrix. These plastics reinforced with glass-fiber will have a long life, light weight and anti-corrosive properties for SO_x. Chimneys having diameter x height : 2.80 m x 185 m (hang type), 2.80 m x 160 m (settle type), 3.10 m x 100 m (settle type) have been made. They are successfully working.

(2) Farm-Pond. In the dry area, water reservoir tanks, made of GF/UP and settled into underground, have been constructed for agricultural use, because of water-tightness, anti-corrosive, easy processing and maintenance and low cost. In our country, it is said about 300 to 400 so-called "farm-ponds" of 1000 3000 m³ capacity are being demanded every year.

(3) Tanks & Vessels. Many large tanks and vessels for chemical plants have been fabricated with GF/UP, because of anti-corrosive, stiff and strong, easy maintenance.

(4) Excrement Tanks. GF/UP tanks of 2.5 3.2 m diameter and 11 m length, which can be loaded on large auto-trucks, are in practical use.

(5) Trailer Car. Large VAN-type trailer cars, which are 11.94 m long, 3.75 m high and 2.48 m wide, have been manufactured of GF/UP.

(6) Boat. A large GF/UP boat has been successfully tested with explosive bursting load.

(7) Carbon Fiber Reinforced Long Span Hybrid Composites Trough for Concrete Bridge. A long GF-CF/UP hybrid trough, installed a water pipeline in its inside, was built in 1979 (3). This trough was attached to a 75 m long prestressed concrete bridge having two interpiers. The trough forms a ca 74 m long tube assembled by 9 sub-assembly pieces 8300 mm long each. Its cross-section has a symmetric closed form consisting of two hat type profiles and an interconnecting plate on the neutral plane. In the upper half space a water pipeline of 100 mm diameter was installed with an attachment support. The extreme fiber portions of the trough were hybridized by glas and carbon cloths with polyester resins. The dimensions of trough section is 600 mm height x 550 mm width. This was the largest hybrid composite structure successfully fabricated in 1979.

(8) Fairing of Transport Aircraft B-767. B-767 is a cooperative development aircraft by Boeing Co., manufacturers of Japan and Italy. The wing-body fairing is the largest composites structural part in B-767, fabricated by a Japanese aircraft maker.

(9) Other Composites Products. There are many other composites products rich in diversity as follows.

Large GF/UP Silos,	Sports Goods,
GF/UP Radomes,	Fishing Tackles,
Rockets,	Wagon for Disabled Person,
Boats,	Medical Apparatus,
Marine Structures,	3500 ton Press,
Automobile Parts,	etc.

(10) Resins and Reinforcements. Anti-corrosive or heat resistant resins and various reinforcing fibers are being developed and produced. The status of reinforcements will be presented by the another author.

(11) Automatic Fabricating Machines. In order to upgrade the reliability of composites, the development of automatic fabricating machines (robots) and high precision fabricating technology have been demanded. In our country, as mentioned before, it needs also future manpower.

A problem in development of such robots seems to be in difficulty for accessing the diversity of kinds and scales of production, especially in the application fields of advanced composites.

Electrical Applications of Composites

As one of more promizing areas of composites, we have an electric application field (4). In this field, there are 3 areas of (a) big current machines, (b) electronics and (c) electric appliances. Among them, (c) is the biggest consumption area of plastics. For (a) and (b), FRP have been used very effectively and successfully. These are very typical application areas of composites in which the electrical and mechanical properties are well hybridized.

In Japan, among the total plastics production of 8.2 million tons in 1979, 0.80 million tons (10%) were used for electric industry. The total production of FRP in 1979 in Japan was ca 0.25 million tons and its 8% was consumed in mechanical and electric industry.

The merits of FRP used in electric industry are the properties of insulation, high specific strength and stiffness, corrosion resistance and capability and flexibility which meet with the design needs of giving the diversity of functions and production scale.

NATIONAL R & D PROJECT FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

In 1981, the Ministry of International Trade and Industry of Government has started a long term R & D project for basic technology of the future industry of Japan.

As the teams concerned with materials, 6 working groups (WG) were organized.

They are WGs for high performance ceramics, synthetic membranes new separation technology, synthetic metals, high performance plastics, advanced alloys with controlled crystalline structures and advanced composite materials.

WG of advanced composite materials, headed by the present author, aims to develop advanced FRP having tensile strength 240 kgf/mm² at 250°C and advanced FRM (Fiber Reinforced Metal) having tensile strength 150 kgf/mm² at 450°C, which would be adapted to use in aero-space and automobile industries. The term is planned to be eight years. In our WG, several companies applied and they are promoting the research and development work of the composites, in cooperation with national research institutes concerned.

CM INFORMATIONS IN JAPAN

There are several societies in our country which have interests in composites. As societies which are fully devoted to composites, we have two : the Japan Society for Composite Materials (JSCM) since 1975 and the Japan Reinforced Plastics (JRPS) since 1955 ; JSCM has the scope ranging from FR Rubber, FR Plastics, FR Metals and the other composites, but JRPS concerns mainly GF/UP. Also the Society for Materials Science, Japan (SMSJ) has a research committee on reinforced plastics (RCRP).

JSCM issues Journal in Japanese and Transactions in English. JRPS issues monthly Journal in Japanese.

The above three societies hold annual joint meeting and symposium every year in cooperating with other societies, in which the proceedings containing extended abstracts are published.

JRPS have the annual Conference with Exhibition ("CONEX") every fall in which besides the paper presentation a pretty large scale exhibition of GFRP raw materials and products and fabricating machines etc. is taken place.

Every fall, we have Japan Plastics Exhibition ("Japan-Plas"), covering all fields of plastics industry.

Universities and institutes are also issuing their research reports in which papers on composites are included.

In Tokyo, we have Japan Science and Technology Information Center.

Recent Symposium on CM

To show the content taken up recently in a CM Symposium in our country, the 11th FRP joint Symposium held in Osaka on March 25 and 26, 1982 is introduced as an example.

This Symposium had the scope of "Creation and Extension of FRP properties", consisting of 6 serial sessions of fatigue (6), modelling and material properties (6), strength of bond and bonded joints (3), mechanical behaviors of structures (3), material testing and NDI (3) and the effect of processing and its residual stress (3), where the number in parenthesis indicates the number of papers. 3 special lectures entitled on : "status of FRP in electric industries", "status and future development of CFRP", and "revelation of CF hybrid characters for GFRP and their cost-performance" were also presented together with a panel discussion on "relationship between research contributions and those utility".

The above content suggests some of a trend and character of recent Symposium in our country.

CONCLUSION

The special needs of CM, status and recent topics in Japan were presented.

Among the needs and content stated above, there might exist some common or similar items in other countries as well.

REFERENCES

1. Statistical Data prepared by Japan Reinforced Plastics Society (JRPS), from 1973 to 1980 ; JRPS-Journal "Reinforced Plastics" Vol.20-27
2. JPRS-Journal "Reinforced Plastics" Vol.28, No.3, 1982, pp.118-120

3. Momoshima S. et al, "Carbon fibre reinforced plastics hybrid long span trough for a bridge-attached water pipeline", Reinforced Plastics, Vol.24, No.7, 1980, pp.210~213.

4. Morita M. et al, "Status of FRP in Electric Industries", Extended Abstract Bulletin, 11th FRP-Symposium, March 1982, pp.67-75.

Table 1. Classification of GFRP with Reference to Production in Japan

Classification	Items	Examples
1. Construction Materials	Flat & corrugated sheets	Dome, Panel, Parts of internal wall & ceiling, Roof
	Other construction mat'ls	Moulds for concrete, Pool, Buoy, Road signals, Built-up house
2. Housing Materials	Bath tub	Bath tub, Unit bath, Shower unit, etc.
	Excrement tank	Excrement tanks, Toilet equipments
3. Marine	Boat, Ship	Float to Hull, All kind parts of boat, Hovercraft, Lifeboat, Leisure boat, Yacht, Fishing boat, Mast, Propeller shaft
4. Transportation	Automobile, Railway wagon	Snow-mobile, Camping trailer, Passenger car, Truck body, Door, Roof, Air-conditioner-duct, Bumper, Instrument panel, Oil & Water tank, Spring
5. Tank & Container	Tank & Container	Water tank, Silo, Foods tank, Transportation box, Container
	Anti-Corrosive	Medical use tank & box, Fan, Electrolysis tank, Anti-corrosive tank
6. Industrial Equipments	Pipe	Pipe made by FW & Pultrusion
	Case	Coding tower, Safety cover, Cases
	Electrical Parts & Goods	Signal element, Printing plate, Insulation goods, Switch box, Battery case, Armature, Support
7. Miscellaneous Goods		Helmet, Manikin, Toy, Chair, Tray Housing interior goods, Sports & Leisure goods
8. Others		Artificial leg, arm & hand, Fishing tackle

Table 2. Shares of Production of Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyester (GF/UP) in Japan, 1973 to 1980

Item	1973	74	75	76	77	78	79	1980	
1. Construction Materials	6.5	8	9	8	7	7	8	9	
2. Housing Materials	50	46	43	43	40	37	34	34	
3. Marine	16	18	21	22	23	26	25	21	
4. Transportation	2	2	2	2	2	1.5	1.5	2	
5. Tank & Container	8	9	9	8	10	10	11	11	
6. Industrial Equipment	7	8	6	6	7	7	8	10	
7. Miscellaneous Goods	4.5	4	5	4	3	3.5	4	4	
8. Others	6	5	5	6	8	8	8.5	9	
Total	%	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	$\frac{\text{Amount}}{\times 10^3 \text{ ton}}$	189	136	124	164	176	204	246	218

Table 3. Shares of Processing Methods of GF/UP
in Japan from 1977 to 1980

Processing Method	1977	1978	1979	1980
Hand Lay-up	52	55	55	45
Spray-up	14	13	12	10
MC	9	11	10	19
Other Press	10	8	8	5
FW	4	4	4	7
CM	9	8	9	11
Others	2	1	2	3
Total %	100	100	100	100

Legend :

GF/UP = Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyester,
 MC = Moulding Compound Method
 FW = Filament Winding
 CM = Continuous Moulding